

CHARACTERISATION OF HYBRID COMPOSITE/METAL INTERFACES USING THE SINGLE CANTILEVER BEAM TEST

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ABSTRACT

Hybrid composite/metal laminates, or fibre-metal laminates, are currently finding applications in the aerospace industry, specifically as fatigue resistant and damage tolerant fuselage materials. In addition, these systems also have considerable potential in the automotive sector, where the difficulties of joining and surface finish of all-composite auto body panels can be overcome by applying a metal skin to the composite part. The durability of these hybrid panels is likely to be dominated by the composite/metal interface. Common techniques for assessing the interfacial bond include lap shear and peel tests. These tests are typically used for screening and are not suitable for generating design data.

The SCB test is a modification of the standard double cantilever beam (DCB) test. Here, one relatively flexible leg is peeled away from the other leg, which is kept rigid by the use of an external stiffener. This test measures mixed-mode interfacial fracture energy, $G_{I/II}$ (J/m^2). Previous studies on aluminium and unidirectional glass-reinforced polypropylene have found that good adhesion is obtained by surface treatment of the metal and incorporation of a modified polymer at the composite/metal interface.

In the current study, SCB tests have been performed in order to evaluate the interfacial fracture properties of specimens manufactured from steel and a woven glass fibre-reinforced polypropylene. Adhesion has been obtained by using a combination of zinc phosphate surface treatment and modified polymer interlayer. The presence of cross-ply fibres at the interface has been found to induce unstable crack growth in SCB specimens.

KEYWORDS: interfacial fracture, fracture toughness, hybrid, composite, laminate

INTRODUCTION

The ever-increasing need for higher performance at lower weight has led to the development of hybrid materials, which combine the advantageous properties of the component materials. Hybrid composite/metal laminates, often referred to as fibre-metal laminates (FMLs), were first developed by the aerospace industry in the 1980s, spawning the ARALL[®] and GLARE[®] materials [1]. These materials, composed of aramid and glass-reinforced epoxy and aluminium, exhibit excellent fatigue resistance, impact resistance and damage tolerance, and are now finding significant application in commercial aircraft [2].

Thermoplastic-based hybrid laminates have received comparatively little attention to date, although thermoplastic composites offer a number of intrinsic advantages over their thermoset-based counterparts. The fast production times, high recyclability and low volatiles offered by thermoplastics make them attractive to automotive manufacturers; the low density and low cost of polypropylene is particularly appealing. Thermoplastic composites have excellent impact absorbing characteristics, which would provide excellent damage tolerance and blast protection in aircraft and security devices.

A few examples of thermoplastic/metal hybrids can be found in the literature. Hylite[®] is an aluminium/polypropylene/aluminium sandwich sheet developed by Corus for use in automotive bonnets. A weight saving of 65% has been reported [3] for a Hylite[®] part over a steel part of equal stiffness, although costs remain prohibitive. The 1998 Ford Focus has a hybrid front-end, manufactured by Dynamit Nobel, using a hybrid technology patented by Bayer AG. Glass-reinforced polyamide is moulded over a steel sub-structure; holes punched in the steel allow the resin to flow through the steel and form rivet-type features [4]. Reportedly, this part has achieved a 40% weight saving, improved mechanical performance and overall cost saving through part integration, when compared to a metal equivalent. However, the presence of holes in the steel make this technology unsuitable for cosmetic applications and load transfer is relatively inefficient with isolated mechanical fasteners. It is therefore necessary to investigate the use of adhesives, as indicated by the hybrid bonded front-end under development by Dow Automotive [5].

In-service performance of hybrid laminates is likely to be interface dominated. Polypropylene, being a polyolefin, is chemically inert, presenting adhesion difficulties. Reyes and Cantwell achieved adhesion between Plytron[®] (Borealis), a unidirectional glass-fibre reinforced polypropylene, and 2024-T0 aluminium alloy by applying an amorphous chromate treatment to the aluminium and incorporating a polypropylene maleic anhydride layer at the interface [6]. These materials were found to have high interfacial fracture toughness ($G_{I/II}=2400\text{J/m}^2$) and excellent impact properties

With specific reference to the automotive industry, the adoption of lightweight composite components into predominantly metal body structures presents a number of problems for automotive manufacturers. These include the difficulties of surface quality and joining. Hybrid laminates of thermoplastic composite and metal can yield significant weight reduction, while obtaining a class-A surface finish and enabling the use of existing painting technology. These materials may also have the potential to be spot-welded into a metal chassis. For reasons of material and assembly costs, steel is still the material of choice for mass produced automotive bodies. So, in this study fracture behaviour of steel-based hybrid laminates is evaluated and compared to those based on aluminium.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURES

The materials under investigation in this study are summarised in Table 1. The thermoplastic composite grade Twintex[®] 4/1 unbalanced was selected to increase flexural stiffness in the testing direction. The metallic materials chosen are standard cold-rolled automotive outer-body strip materials used on current production vehicles.

Material	Grade	Description	Thickness (mm)	Supplier
Thermoplastic composite	Twintex [®] 4/1	Woven, commingled 60% glass-reinforced polypropylene	0.5mm	Saint-Gobain Vetrotex
Steel	DC04/DC05	Cold rolled, 0.002%C	0.8mm	Corus
Aluminium	6111	Cold rolled, T4 aged	0.9mm	Alcan

Table 1. Summary of the materials under investigation

Adhesion between the thermoplastic composite and metal has been achieved by surface pre-treatment of the metal and incorporation of a modified polymer at the composite/metal interface. In a previous study, the effect of various surface treatments on thermoplastic composite/metal adhesion was investigated [7]. Phosphating and anodising were identified as suitable surface pre-treatments for steel and aluminium respectively. Standard automotive zinc phosphating (coating weight 2-3g/m²) and passivation was carried out by Henkel Surface Technologies. Sulphuric acid anodising (SAA) was carried out by J.A. Baddeley & Co Ltd (coating thickness ca. 5µm). The topography of the surface treated metals has been evaluated using a JEOL 35C scanning electron microscope (SEM). The polymer interlayer materials employed were a polypropylene adhesive film XAF 23.101 40g/m² (Sarna Xiro) and Fusabond[®] M613-05 (DuPont), a maleic anhydride modified polypropylene (PP-MAH). The PP-MAH was supplied in granular form and converted to sheets by compression in a heated press. Previous work has shown that adhesive bond-line thickness has a significant influence on the bond strength. Small scale studies have indicated that optimum adhesion is achieved when using 0.14mm PP film thickness and 0.26mm PP-MAH thickness after moulding.

The hybrid systems studied are summarised in Table 2. One plaque of each type was produced by non-isothermal compression moulding of pre-heated material stacks. Twelve layers of glass-PP were used to obtain a composite thickness of 6mm. A layer of aluminium foil was inserted between the metal and polymer interlayer to obtain a pre-crack. The stacks were heated in a R. Royce 4.5kW infrared oven until the glass-PP bulk temperature reached 180°C. Once heated, they were transferred manually, in less than 10 seconds, to a Bradley & Turton 150 tonne hydraulic press and moulded at 50bar pressure in a simple flat plaque tool preheated to 80°C.

Four test specimens were cut from each moulded plaque using a tungsten carbide tipped circular saw blade. The section of metal arm at the point of loading was removed carefully using a hacksaw; a 0.2mm brass shim was inserted between composite and metal arms to prevent damage to the composite during cutting. In order to ensure rigidity of the metal arm, 25mm mild steel square tube stiffeners were bonded to the metal arm using Araldite[®]2015 (Vantico) a silica-toughened epoxy adhesive. Both substrates were given a simple abrasive wipe with Scotchbrite[®] MX-SR (3M) and degreased with acetone prior to bonding. After the adhesive was applied, specimens were clamped in a purpose built jig and left for 24 hours for the adhesive to cure. Any traces of adhesive on the specimen edges were removed using a knife and fine silicon carbide abrasive paper. The edges were then painted with white correction fluid for contrast and marked with a 5mm division metric scale from the position of the pre-crack.

A schematic diagram of the SCB test specimen is shown in Figure 1. The width B was 25mm, span L was 125mm, initial crack length a₀ was 40mm, leaving approximately 10mm from loading member to the end of the composite arm. Testing was performed on an Instron 1195 universal testing machine fitted with a 50kN load cell (2kN full scale load). Crosshead displacement was

set to 1mm/min. Crack length was monitored by eye and readings of load and displacement taken for every 5mm increment. The test was stopped when the crack length had exceeded 60mm.

Code	Composite	Interlayer	Metal	Surface Treatment
A	Woven glass-PP	PP adhesive film	Steel DC04	Zinc phosphate
B	Woven glass-PP	PP maleic anhydride	Steel DC04	Zinc phosphate
C	Woven glass-PP	PP adhesive film	Aluminium 6111	Anodise (SAA)
D	Woven glass-PP	PP maleic anhydride	Aluminium 6111	Anodise (SAA)

Table 2. Summary of hybrid systems studied in this programme.

Figure 1. Schematic of the single cantilever beam (SCB) test geometry.

Data reduction was performed using an experimental compliance method developed by Reyes and Cantwell [6]. This is based on Equation 1, the general formula for strain energy release rate or fracture energy G :

$$G = \frac{P^2}{2b} \frac{dC}{da} \quad [1]$$

Where P is load (N), b is width (m), C is compliance (m/N) and a is crack length (m).

Specimen compliance is calculated using Equation 2 and plotted against the cube of crack length (a^3) and a curve fit of the form shown in Equation 3 applied.

$$C = \frac{\delta}{P} \quad [2]$$

$$C = C_0 + ka^3 \quad [3]$$

Where δ is deflection (m). Parameters C_0 and k are constants for a given specimen; k is measured from the slope of the graph of C vs. a^3 .

Equation 3 can be differentiated with respect to crack length to obtain Equation 4:

$$\frac{dC}{da} = 3ka^2 \quad [4]$$

Equation 4 can be substituted into Equation 1 to obtain Equation 5, the formula for mixed-mode fracture energy:

$$G_{I/II} = \frac{3P^2ka^2}{2B} \quad [5]$$

The fracture surfaces of tested SCB specimens were examined using optical and electron microscopy to determine fracture behaviour. A Nikon stereoscope was used to observe fracture surfaces at low magnification. High magnification examination was performed on a Philips XL30 ESEM-FEG at 10kV in high vacuum mode. To avoid charging of the non-conductive media, specimens were gold coated on a EMSCOPE SC 500 coating machine at 15mA for 4 minutes.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

SEM micrographs of the phosphating and anodising surface treatments are displayed in Figure 2. Along with the improvements in chemical bonding that the surface treatments provide, significant benefits in mechanical bonding are expected. The phosphated steel surface is covered in randomly oriented zinc phosphate crystals, which should provide significant mechanical keying for the polymer. The anodised aluminium surface contains anodic pores, which should also induce mechanical bonding.

Figure 2. SEM micrographs of metal surface treatments, (a) phosphated steel, (b) anodised aluminium.

Typical force-displacement curves from the SCB tests, comparing the two interlayer polymers, are shown in Figure 3. Both curves have a linear portion to start, followed by a yield point, caused by crack initiation, and then a gradual decay in force with displacement due to crack propagation. The curve for the PP film exhibits a steady decay in the region, characteristic of stable crack growth, whereas the PP-MAH curve contains several steps, which suggests unstable or semi-stable crack growth.

Figure 4 contains typical plots of C vs. a^3 , used during the data reduction. The data clearly follows a linear trend, from which the slope can be calculated with confidence.

Figure 3. Typical force-displacement curves for steel-based SCB specimens.

Figure 4. Typical plot of C vs. a^3 following an SCB test on steel-based specimens.

Following data reduction, fracture energy can be plotted against crack length to obtain crack growth resistance curves. Typical examples of these curves for the two interlayers are displayed in Figure 5. As the crack propagates, the fracture energy (resistance to crack growth) increases until it reaches a plateau, which represents the fracture energy of the interface. This resistance effect is thought to be caused by fibre-bridging in the wake of the crack.

Figure 5. Typical resistance curves for steel-based SCB specimens.

Figure 6 summarises the average fracture energy results for the hybrid systems investigated. The error bars represent the standard deviation of the data. The fracture energies of the hybrid interfaces are 3000-5000J/m², impressive figures when compared to thermoset-based adhesive joints and composites. The PP-MAH interlayer performs better, in terms of fracture energy, than the PP adhesive film interlayer for both metals. Fracture surfaces of tested SCB specimens are displayed in Figure 7. Failure in the PP film systems is a mixture of cohesive failure of the adhesive and interlayer/metal interface fracture. For the PP-MAH based hybrids, crack growth is predominantly in the woven glass-PP composite, with a small amount of interlayer/metal interfacial fracture also present. To cause preferential crack propagation in the composite, the PP-MAH/metal interface must clearly be very tough and explains the higher fracture energy in the PP-MAH systems.

The PP-MAH performs better with aluminium than with steel. Comparing Figure 7 (c) and (d), there is a greater amount of composite failure, compared to interfacial failure, for the aluminium substrate, indicating better interlayer/metal adhesion. It is likely that the active MAH molecules in PP-MAH form stronger bonds with the oxide groups on the anodised aluminium surface than with the zinc phosphate. The PP film interlayer appears to perform slightly better with steel than aluminium, opposing the behaviour of the PP-MAH. The difference is slight and could be accounted for in the experimental scatter.

Figure 6. Summary of the interfacial fracture properties of steel and aluminium-based systems.

Figure 7. Low magnification optical micrographs of fractured SCB specimens, (a) steel/PP film, (b) steel/PP-MAH, (c) aluminium/PP film and (d) aluminium/PP-MAH.

By looking at the fracture surfaces of the metal substrate at high magnification it is possible to make further assessments on failure loci and failure mechanisms (Figure 8). The fracture surfaces of specimens with PP adhesive film interlayer are covered in extruded polymer strands, caused by

ductile cohesive failure of the PP film, near the interlayer/metal interface. There appears to be greater coverage of these strands on the phosphated steel than on the anodised aluminium, indicating slightly better adhesion. For the PP-MAH-based specimens, representative areas of residual composite were examined. The presence of fibre indentations on the fracture surface, but few actual fibres, indicate failure at the fibre/matrix interface of the first layer of glass-PP. Polymeric strands are present between the fibres and some areas of more brittle failure can also be seen. The matrix PP has a carbon black filler which is likely to cause more brittle fracture behaviour, compared to the PP-MAH. This suggests significant mixing of matrix PP and PP-MAH has occurred.

Figure 8. SEM optical micrographs of fracture surfaces of metal substrates after SCB testing of (a) steel/PP film, (b) steel/PP-MAH, (c) aluminium/PP film and (d) aluminium/PP-MAH.

CONCLUSIONS

Good adhesion is obtained between a woven glass-polypropylene and metal, when using a combination of metal surface pre-treatment and a modified polymer interlayer. Standard automotive zinc phosphating and sulphuric acid anodising are suitable treatments for steel and aluminium respectively, by providing improved chemical and mechanical adhesion. A polypropylene (PP) adhesive film and a maleic anhydride modified polypropylene (PP-MAH) are suitable polymer interlayers.

The fracture energies of four hybrid systems have been assessed by using a single cantilever beam (SCB) test, and have found to be of magnitude $3000\text{-}5000\text{J/m}^2$. The PP-MAH interlayer produces a tough interface, causing crack propagation in the composite, and hence promotes

greater fracture energy. PP-MAH interlayer/metal adhesion is greater for aluminium than steel, possibly due to improved bonding of MAH groups to the anodic oxide layer. The systems with PP film interlayer failed by a combination of cohesive and interlayer/metal interfacial mechanisms. Examination of fracture surfaces at high magnification confirms that the PP film adheres slightly better to the phosphated steel than the anodised aluminium. Failure in PP-MAH systems is predominantly at the fibre/matrix interface of the first layer of glass-PP composite.

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REFERENCES

1. Gunnink, J.W., Verbruggen, M.L.C.E., Vogelesang, L.B., "ARALL, a light weight structural material for impact and fatigue sensitive structures", *Vertica*, Vol. 10, No. 2, 1986, pp. 241-254.
2. Vogelesang, L.B., Vlot, A., "Development of fibre metal laminates for advanced aerospace structures", *Journal of Materials Processing Technology*, Vol. 103, 2000, pp. 1-5.
3. Veenstra, E.W., "Aluminium-plastic-aluminium sandwich for maximum weight reduction in body panels", *SAE Transactions*, No. 930706, 1993.
4. Meurer, E., "Plastic/metal hybrid technology in automotive front ends", *SAE Transactions*, No. 1999-01-3243, 1999.
5. "Bonded front-end relieves stress", *Reinforced Plastics*, Vol. 46, No. 5, May 2002, pp. 7.
6. Reyes, G., Cantwell, W.J., "The mechanical properties of fibre-metal laminates based on glass fibre reinforced polypropylene", *Composites Science and Technology*, Vol. 60, 2000, pp.1085-1094.
7. Weager, B.M., Rudd, C.D., "Evaluation of the interface durability of hybrid composite/metal laminates for lightweight automotive body structures", *ECCM-10 Conference*, Brugge, Belgium, 3-6 June 2001.